

The Principle of Least Variation On Lorentz Manifolds

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Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constant equation in its first representation, i.e. the magnitudes of interactions and in particular, the ratio of net variations to total variations N_V/T_V a series converging to zero appear. The higher the net variations the $N_V \rightarrow \infty$ closer to zero the ratio. The conclusion of the coupling constant series in the magnitude representation is that the most significant interactions on the Lorentz manifold are those with the biggest ratio of total to net. The biggest ratio is related to the smallest amount of net variations $N_V \rightarrow 0$.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.1}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \tag{1.11}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{2}$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ... \tag{3}$$

In the thesis, we derived the coupling constant as a ration between total arbitrary variations to the net variations, $N(V)$, which are outside the parenthesis. Those net variations are a different representation of curvature on the Lorentz manifold. Notice the numerical relations between the total to net:

$$/T_V \tag{4} \qquad R = N_V$$

$$\frac{1}{9} = 0.111 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{3}{30} = 0.1 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{5}{128} = 0.039 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{7}{850} = 0.008 \quad (8)$$

$$0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots \quad (9)$$

The reasoning was clear, as the coupling constant equation is multiplies each even sum of the previous element in the next prime, and the net variations are the prime numbers sequence itself. In means that each element the net curvature is a smaller and smaller portion of the whole variation cluster, which reason why the sequence is getting weaker and weaker. Based on this equation we can vividly derive and predict the weakness of gravity. We can say that nature is aspiring to minimize the ratio of net to total. All the possible amount of curvature can and will appear and nature, but the most common and noticeable ones are those with the bigger ratio, or least amount of net variation:

$$0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots \rightarrow 0 \quad (10)$$

The bosons in which we are already know of. The interactions associated with the number one, three and five. The two lowest primes and one. The 8 – theory principle, which is derived by this analysis, is the **principle of Least Variation** or curvature as we are dealing with a Lorenz manifold. Just as Feynman did in quantum path integrations, all is taken into account. however, the most significant routes are the simplest ones. In the 8-theory framework the most significant Interactions are those with the largest ratios between the net variations to the total Variations The largest ratios are those with the least curvature or smallest prime numbers and the number one, and primes are representing manifold variations.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)